

D3.1 – Technology Demonstrations -V3

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D3.1 Technology Demonstrations – V3

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Abstract

This report is the third version of BIMprove's Deliverable 3.1. *Technology Demonstration*. The report describes the functional elements developed in BIMprove. It has been updated with newer results after the end of each cycle marking M12, M19 and M25. The report demonstrates a wide range of BIMprove developments covering stationary, ground- and UAV-based data acquisition systems; augmented reality (AR) visualisation of BIM model; application of multi-user virtual reality (VR); computer vision model for detection of safety structures in the construction site; mapping of point clouds to IFC elements; and BIMprove web front end. This document provides a snapshot and a short description of each development, and refers to the BIMprove video depository, where the development are more comprehensively demonstrated through video recordings.

Keywords

Technology demonstrations; demos; functionalities

Revisions

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AR	Augmented Reality
BCF	BIM Collaboration Format
BIM	Building Information Modelling
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
MUVR	Multi User Virtual Reality
VR	Virtual Reality
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
IR	Infrared Radiation

BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that **BIMprove** system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

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Context

Scope: This report is the third version of BIMprove's Deliverable 3.1. Technology Demonstration. The report describes the functional elements developed in BIMprove. It has been updated with newer results after the end of each cycle marking M12, M19 and M25. The report demonstrates a wide range of BIMprove developments covering stationary, ground- and UAV-based data acquisition systems; augmented reality (AR) visualisation of BIM model; application of multi-user virtual reality (VR); computer vision model for detection of safety structures in the construction site; mapping of point clouds to IFC elements; and BIMprove web front end. This document provides a snapshot and a short description of each development, and refers to the BIMprove video depository, where the development are more comprehensively demonstrated through video recordings.

BIMprove: The BIMprove project (Improving Building Information Modelling by Realtime Tracing of Construction Processes) is intended to demonstrate how key processes can be automated and how the digital twin concept, representing a dynamic and expanding image of a real building asset, can benefit the management of a building throughout its life cycle. The overall objective of the BIMprove project is to go beyond the static BIM approach and create a digital thread that acts as a dynamic metrical building model, a digital twin. This will promote the easy monitoring of construction site status, effective resource scheduling and improved work planning. The new technology will offer greater levels of flexibility and safety, and enhanced productivity.

Audience: This report targets all active organisations along the construction value chain including contractors; suppliers of building materials, chemical and construction equipment; architecture and engineering firms; building owners and developers. Government authorities, which may impact the future of the industry via regulations and standardisation, or act as the main procurer of the construction projects, are also a targeted audience. Furthermore, this reports targes also members of academia and research institutes as a resource to foster effective collaboration and build upon BIMprove project in the future.

Foreword

BIMprove project will invest in the development of a system that promotes fast-track productivity by cutting costs and improving working conditions by employing 3D model-based BIM systems in combination with a digital twin technology to the construction sector, constituting a dynamic and multi-functional system based on real-time data. The technology will enable a real-time status overview of all construction sites, facilitating the early identification of errors and their remediation at the lowest possible cost. It will also be possible to control resource scheduling and transactions in real time, hence, ensuring high levels of construction site security and efficient adherence to, and adaptation of, work schedules, according to need. The technology is actualised using ground-based robots and unmanned aerials vehicles (UAVs) to monitor site status and detect deviations that can be used to update the digital twin and the underlying BIM model. It will facilitate the anonymous tracking of site personnel, thus enabling both the system and personnel supervisors to optimize resource allocation, personnel flow, and worker safety. The BIMprove system will be easily accessible to all stakeholders in the form of various user interfaces, including the provision of notifications to site workers via wearable devices, and to supervisors via virtual reality (VR) visualisations. The system will be a cloud-based service with a layered structure, enabling the addition of future extensions, as required.

The BIMprove system will be developed in a series of six-monthly iterative cycles, which will ensure adequate time for the fine-tuning of system functionalities to meet the requirements of the consortium's industry partners. This aim of this report is to demonstrate developed functional elements of the BIMprove system after the first 18 months of the project. This report firstly introduces the overall BIMprove data architecture, which provides an outlook of the anticipated technology developed throughout the project. Afterwards, it provides a snapshot and a short description of each of the developed functionalities and demonstrates them through video recordings, which will be stored in the BIMprove video depository and can be accessed by the targeted audience and the public through the provided link.

The BIMprove Data Architecture

The BIMprove system is constructed from some loosely coupled data interfaces that each provide sporadic information updates, while the core element, referred to as a 'backend', provides highly integrated and near real time information exchange for use in data analytics and visualization services, as described in the BIMprove requirements list.

Figure 1. The main components of BIMprove data architecture

The main components of the BIMprove data architecture are visualized in the figure above, and described in the following:

Proprietary 3D design tools. Building asset designers (architects and engineers) will work using their own applications, such as Revit, ArchiCAD, Tekla, MagiCAD, DDS and Allplan, in the same way as they do today. In a BIMprove context, such tools will output in open BIM (IFC) models that illustrate the 'as-designed' appearance of the building asset that includes not only its 3D-geometry but also rich information on physical elements such as slabs, walls and windows, as well as non-physical elements such as rooms, building storeys, zones, systems and design layers. If any design changes are initiated from BIMprove, these will be issued by BCF.

Construction schedules. Provided they exist, highly detailed (daily) construction schedules will be stored in a variety of highly heterogeneous ways, and may be exchanged using IFC (e.g., IfcTask). However, such exchanges will only be carried out very rarely. BIMprove will enable data entry either manually or by another standardized approach, such as by using a predefined scheme.

VR/AR. Data visualization is one of the main benefits of digital twins. Geometry derived from IFC (with intact identifiers) can be presented on demand in VR and AR applications, and users can return tasks/issues to the backend using BCF.

UxV stations. Drones and mobile ground exploration robots are not directly connected to the backend, but communicate indirectly via intermediate stations, which obtain their data from the backend to plan their UxV reality capture paths. These paths are based on data from the future construction and its location, taken from the schedule and BIM models. The stations send back point clouds, aligned with the coordinate system of the BIM models, together with geometry derived from the point clouds and thermal photos.

Digital twin serialization. In contrast to a BIM file, a BIMprove digital twin cannot simply be exported from or transferred between construction sites. This raises the question of how a digital twin, representing the sum of all information, can be accessed after the project end date. We propose to develop a strategy for the serialisation of key data, including revisions and time stamps so that the content of the main data entities can be restored outside the system. Our aim is to achieve this as far as is practically possible using open standards such as IFC for BIM, open point cloud formats, open image formats, BCF for issue history, etc.

Construction stakeholders. The various stakeholders will be presented with the information that they have to consider and decide on. For example, a scanning function may be introduced to see if security protection is present when it should be. This will enable decision-makers to inspect the point cloud (perhaps accompanied by a system-generated suggestion), determine whether a deviation has occurred and, if so, decide what the next step should be.

BIM at the site office or off-site. It will be possible to visualise and analyse a wide range of information both at the site office and off-site. Information from scans, as-designed BIM, schedules, etc., will be made available from the backend and viewed on a big screen or in virtual reality. Questions and decisions that require human intervention can be sent to the backend using BCF.

Sensor gateway. Sensor data such as worker or truck positions are sent to the backend via the gateways. Urgent warning notifications, such as a truck reversing towards a worker, are sent directly to the worker or truck, and not via the backend.

Technology Demonstrations

Overview

Description: The video documents the project's meeting at the PUC-site in Madrid. Even though it was not made to be a technology-demonstration-video, it does show some of the BIMprove features, as shown in the screenshots:

- Safety net BCF-feature in the XR Viewer
- pyBIMprove heatmap representation of scanned pointclouds, visualized in VR

Snapshot of the demo:

Figure 2 Screenshots from the meeting in Madrid

Link to video:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/demos/>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DKSW7HXamVo>

Multi-User, Multi-Location, Multi-Device XR Viewer

Where: PUC Lausanne

When: 23 - 25 November 2022

Description: The demo shows an example of how the BIMprove XR-Viewer is used at the PUC-site in Lausanne Bussigny. It demonstrates not only the multi-user functionality but also, how the system works with users joining from multiple locations (Geneva, Lausanne, Stuttgart) and with multiple different devices (VR-HMD, 3D-game-style PC, Tablet).

There are two videos to demonstrate this. The first one shows four parties meeting in VR to discuss a construction issue. It contains audio-narration.

The second one shows the same scenes with more in-depth views of the use of the graphical user interfaces within the XR-Viewer. It has no additional narration but complements the first video.

Snapshot of the demo:

Figure 3 Some highlights from PUC Lausanne

Link to video:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/demos/>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iYv9pU5YQJU>

Asset Localization and Tracking (ALT)

Where: PUC Fyrstikkbakken

When: 2022-09-24/P4D

Description: The library for ALT was implemented in the Python package *ble_tracking*. With the package, tracking of mobile beacons (tags) can be performed based on only RSSI over zones defined by a set of stationary beacons mounted at known geometric locations. The stationary beacons may be BluEpyc EchoBeacons or ordinary Bluetooth receivers, such as found in laptops and Raspberry Pis. *ble_tracking* comprises some 2000 lines of Python code (counted with *sloccount*)

The *ble_tracking* library includes a live tracker visualizer, TagTrackerGui, for testing and tuning.

In addition, some couple of hundred lines of Python code (counted with *sloccount*) was implemented for analysis of tag tracker performances over data recorded at Fyrstikkbakken 14.

Experiments were conducted on the entire 4th floor comprising eight rooms. A challenge was the packaged bathrooms standing in five of the rooms. This is, however, a realistic challenge.

10 BluEpyc EchoBeacons were set up to cover the eight rooms. Two BluEpyc Gateways were set up to cover sampling from the EchoBeacons. Recording of signals from all EchoBeacons via the Gateways was performed on one single PC running all nodes of the distributed system.

A fixed route covering all rooms was repeatedly traversed by an operator. The route was traced at a reasonably slow pace to ensure separation of signals in later analysis.

Over the fixed route eight recordings over four different scenarios were performed:

- Single operator. One tag in helmet. No other tags. Two identical trials.
- Single operator. One tag in helmet. 10 other tags as noise. One trial with the noise tags distributed under the EchoBeacons, and one trial with all noise tags concentrated at “room_west”. Tracking only on tag in helmet.
- Single operator. One tag in helmet, one tag in pocket, one tag in hand. Three identical trials. Tracking on all tags.
- Two operators, one with tag in helmet, hand, and pocket, and one with only tag in helmet. Tracking on all tags.

For each trial the stream of observations from the two Gateways was recorded, and an execution log of timestamps of operator transitions between zones was saved.

Analysis consists in tuning signal filter and tag tracker parameters for reliability in terms of matching between transitions from tracker and execution log, and responsiveness of tracker transitions with

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corresponding execution log transitions. It is important to note that matching transitions is a prerequisite for analysing for responsiveness in a given tracker output.

Simple, experimental tuning to conservative filter and tracker parameters shows some expected results:

- Single tag in helmet gives good matching and a responsiveness of a couple of seconds.
- Tag in hand or pocket gives weak and intermittent signals resulting in no or poor matching.
- Tag in helmet with other tags around can give matching but a poor responsiveness of up to 20 seconds.

Quantitative analysis is being worked on. However, already the high response times observed in the scenarios with multiple tags suggests that an early warning system for workers cannot be based on the current technology, or the current implementation for using it.

Snapshot of the demo:

Figure 4 Summary of ALT tests

Link to video:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/demos/>

Update on VR engine and point cloud shaders

Where: PUC Fyrstikkbakken

When: 22-27 September 2022

Description: We have decided to update Unity 2019 LTS to Unity 2021 LTS for our development in BIMprove to get better performance and to support a wider range of HMDs without individual adaptations using OpenXR. Stable and reliable OpenXR-Packages are available for Unity 2021 (and later) only.

This Update is ongoing.

In the current version (before the update) of the XR Viewer, pointclouds are rendered using DirectX 11 and geometric shaders to create small discs for every point of the respective pointcloud.

Other rendering APIs such as OpenGL and Vulkan allow to use point shaders with the possibility to adjust the size of the rendered points. Compatibility issues regard OpenGL and the OpenXR-Packages of Unity prevented the rendering of interaction gizmos and other parts of the user interface. The more recent rendering API Vulkan doesn't show these issues. So Vulkan has been chosen to render the VR applications of BIMprove. The performance of OpenGL and Vulkan was quite equal in our tests.

Using the more efficient point shader and Vulkan increased the performance measured in frame rates significantly. The pointclouds are now rendered as single squares. Our first approach rendered the points as discs.

The screenshots show two examples using the "old" disc shader and four using the point shader that shows the points as squares.

Snapshot of the demo:

Figure 5 Shader updates

Link to video:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/demos/>

Mixed Reality (MR) visualization of the BIM Model at construction site

Where: PUC Lausanne

When: 23-25 November 2022

Description: BIM@Construction tools was demonstrated in real construction site with Microsoft HoloLens 2 and Android tablet devices. BIM Model could be visualized in AR in 1st and 3rd person point of view. Also, user is able put on / off various layer e.g. electricity, ventilation,... and using MR tools such as measurement.

Snapshot of the demo:

Figure 6 Usage of MR tools

Link to video:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/demos/>

<https://youtu.be/nveo16orX1w>

Updates in safety element detection

Where: PUC Madrid

When: 07. October 2022

Description: Computer vision model has been updated with training with photos including more variation in types of safety elements.

The results of the image analysis engine can be transformed into BCF issues in Bimsync.

The computer vision functionalities are provided as a service with web-ui and REST interface for integration.

Snapshot of the demo:

Figure 7 Safety element detection

Link to video:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/demos/>

IR images & Bimsync integration

Where: PUC Lausanne

When: 23-25 November 2022

Description: The following procedure has been tested:

- Take a picture on the drone (in a manual way in this case)
- Assign the position/orientation info in the exif-data of the image (in the BIM frame)
- Check, if temperature is above threshold
- If yes: send image to backend, there, a BCF issue is automatically generated, this is sent to the fire manager of the project. Since the position data is in the photo, it is directly led to the correct position/viewpoint in the model

Link to video:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/demos/>

3D scanning using Robotnik UGV (RB-Summit XL)

Where: PUC Lausanne

When: 23-25 November 2022

Description: The test scope included scanning selected apartments at the construction site. The following points have been reported:

- The scanning during work hours in often occupied areas is challenging due to inaccuracies caused by constantly moving construction employees.
- The time of a single scanning position takes between 4-5, including the time of changing the robot's position between them. That procedure includes the scanning time (2minutes 50second), changing position (30 seconds - 1 minute) and stabilization scanner assembled to the mast.
- One apartment was scanned using a Matterport camera and laser scanner from the robot - that is why one might have data for accuracy comparison.
- The weight of the robot might cause damage to the existing door thresholds
- The pointcloud generated has 178.761.358 points and a size of 4,6 GB

Snapshot of the demo:

Figure 8 Pointclouds recorded

Link to video:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/demos/>